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Mental Evolution of Youth in Divided Societies: In the Light of the Qur'an and Hadith

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Mental Evolution of Youth in Divided Societies: In the Light of the Qur'an and Hadith

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ABSTRACT

Divided societies are usually affected by internal conflicts, racial and linguistic prejudices, and sectarian divisions, which lead to instability. The greatest impact of such conditions falls on the youth, as they are the most dynamic, sensitive, and future-building segment of society. Young people growing up in such an environment often face mental disturbance, intellectual confusion, insecurity, and an identity crisis, which not only hinder the development of their personality but also leave negative effects on society at large. The mental evolution of youth is therefore extremely important, as it shapes their attitudes, decisions, and social roles. If this process is built on positive and balanced foundations, the youth can become guarantors of social harmony and development; otherwise, they may become a cause of further conflict and division. This research studies the mental evolution of youth in the light of the Qur'an and Hadith and clarifies how Islamic teachings provide principles of intellectual maturity, moral training, social consciousness, and positive character building for the youth. The Qur'an and Sunnah are not only a source of spiritual satisfaction and moral guidance for the youth but also shape their personality in such a way that they rise above differences and play their role for collective welfare. Islamic teachings emphasize principles such as the pursuit of knowledge, moderation, justice, patience, tolerance, cooperation, and unity, which protect the youth from the effects of division and conflict, and at the same time incline them towards constructive activities. The basic objective of this research is to understand the mental evolution of youth in the context of Islamic teachings and to examine how, in the light of the Qur'an and Sunnah, their intellectual training can make them a group that plays a positive role in divided societies. The results of this study indicate that if the mental and intellectual development of youth is built on religious foundations, they can become guarantors of peace, harmony, and development instead of conflict and division. Thus, Islam provides such a comprehensive framework that grants youth mental evolution not only

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at the individual level but also enables them to play an effective role at the collective level.

Keywords: Youth, Mental Evolution, Divided Societies, Qur'an and Hadith, Intellectual Maturity, Social Harmony, Islamic Teachings, Character Building.

The young generation is considered the backbone of any nation. Their mental and intellectual development shapes the future of society. But when a society falls into division upon division, where racial, linguistic, religious, or group prejudices prevail, negative effects are cast on the mental evolution of the youth. The generation growing up in such societies generally suffers from mental anxiety, intellectual confusion, and an identity crisis. Their energies are wasted in conflict and discord instead of constructive activity, which ultimately becomes an obstacle to the progress of society. Islam has placed special emphasis on the mental and intellectual training of youth. In the Holy Qur'an, Allah Almighty has clearly stated:

إِنَّهُمْ فِتْيَةٌ آمَنُوا بِرَبِّهِمْ وَزِدْنَاهُمْ هُدًى ﴿١٣﴾^١

Translation: "Indeed, they were youths who believed in their Lord, and We increased them in guidance."

This verse highlights the fact that when the youth establish their mental evolution on the foundation of faith and guidance, Allah Almighty grants them further guidance and steadfastness. Similarly, it is stated in the Holy Qur'an:

وَاعْتَصِمُوا بِحَبْلِ اللَّهِ جَمِيعًا وَلَا تَفَرَّقُوا^٢

Translation: "And hold firmly to the rope of Allah all together and do not become divided."

This verse especially teaches the youth to make unity and harmony a part of their intellectual and practical life instead of division and differences. In the Hadith as well, special attention has been given to the role and mental evolution of the youth. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) said:

سَبْعَةٌ يُظِلُّهُمُ اللَّهُ يَوْمَ الْقِيَامَةِ فِي ظِلِّهِ ، يَوْمَ لَا ظِلَّ إِلَّا ظِلُّهُ : إِمَامٌ عَادِلٌ ، وَشَابٌّ نَشَأَ فِي عِبَادَةِ اللَّهِ^٣

Translation: "Seven (people) will be shaded by Allah by His Shade on the Day of Resurrection when there will be no shade except His Shade. (They will be), a just ruler, a young man who has been brought up in the worship of Allah."

This Hadith makes it clear that if the youth establish their mental and intellectual training on the basis of worship, faith, and morality, they will succeed in this world and the Hereafter. Similarly, the Holy Prophet (peace be upon him) said:

اٰغْتَنِمْ خَمْسًا قَبْلَ خَمْسٍ: شَبَابَكَ قَبْلَ هَرَمِكَ وَصِحَّتَكَ قَبْلَ سَقَمِكَ وَغِنَاكَ قَبْلَ فُقْرِكَ
وَفَرَاغَكَ قَبْلَ شُغْلِكَ وَحَيَاتَكَ قَبْلَ مَوْتِكَ"^٢

Translation: "Take five things as a blessing before the other five things. Your youth before your old age, your health before your illness, your affluence before your poverty, your leisure before your occupation, and your life before your death."

This blessed saying highlights the value of youth and the importance of mental evolution in this period.

In the light of these texts, it is evident that the Qur'an and Hadith provide the youth with such an intellectual and practical framework that makes their personality balanced, positive, and influential even in divided societies. Islam teaches the youth unity, tolerance, patience, the pursuit of knowledge, and justice so that they may incline towards development and construction instead of social conflict. In divided societies, the intellectual growth and mental evolution of youth can be improved in the light of the teachings of the Qur'an and Hadith. The purpose of this process is not merely to state theoretical principles but to introduce such practical methods that help the youth in refining their personality. In this way, they can establish peace in society, promote mutual unity, and become guarantors of collective development.

Mental Evolution of Youth in the Light of the Qur'an

The Holy Qur'an provides guidance and light for every aspect of human life, and it also presents a comprehensive and balanced framework for the mental evolution of youth. Youth is the stage of life in which personality, thought, and character are formed. This period is full of possibilities, yet it is not free from dangers and intellectual deviations. That is why the Qur'an has set clear principles for the intellectual and practical training of youth.

The Foundation of Faith and Guidance

The fundamental root of the intellectual growth and mental evolution of youth is faith. Faith grants a kind of intellectual maturity that protects them from negative influences and directs them towards a positive path. In the Holy Qur'an, the mention of the People of the Cave makes this reality clear. They were young men living in a society where false beliefs and un-Islamic ideologies prevailed, but they refused to accept the pressure of that environment by having complete faith in their Lord. Through faith, they succeeded in preserving their intellectual freedom and in being protected from misguidance. This event is a shining example for the youth that if faith is strong, then external pressure, negative attitudes, or false ideologies cannot affect their mental evolution. Faith grants them steadfastness, courage, and determination, and also enables them to shape their personality along positive lines. In this way, faith not only provides a theoretical foundation but also guides youth on a practical level so that they may protect themselves from social corruption and become guarantors of peace, brotherhood, and the construction of society.

The Pursuit of Knowledge and Intellectual Broadening

The pursuit of knowledge is a natural need of man which becomes a means of his mental evolution and intellectual broadening. Knowledge grants man access to reality, the ability to make correct decisions, and the capacity to solve social problems. When youth make the acquisition of knowledge their first priority, their thinking expands, and instead of viewing things from a limited perspective, they begin to understand them in a broader context. Intellectual broadening means that a person should not remain confined only to his environment or personal experiences but should enrich his thinking through different sources of knowledge, observations, and study. In the Holy Qur'an, emphasis has repeatedly been laid on the importance of acquiring knowledge, and the Holy Prophet (peace be upon him) has declared it obligatory for every Muslim. That is why the quest for knowledge and intellectual broadening not only shows youth the path of personal development but also makes them capable of playing a positive, constructive, and purposeful role for society. The Qur'an describes knowledge as light and ignorance as darkness. For the youth, the most important aspect is that they nurture their mental development on the basis of knowledge.

قُلْ بَلْ يَسْتَوِي الَّذِينَ يَعْلَمُونَ وَالَّذِينَ لَا يَعْلَمُونَ^٥

Translation: "Are those who know equal to those who do not know?"

This verse draws the attention of youth to the fact that intellectual maturity and evolution are possible only through knowledge.

The Spirit of Patience and Steadfastness

The ups and downs of life play an important role in the personality and mental training of youth. Difficulties and trials actually create endurance, courage, and practical insight within them. The Holy Qur'an provides guidance to the youth that patience and steadfastness are the real path to success. When youth adopt patience as their principle, they not only remain safe from social pressure and negative influences but also, by maintaining moderation and balance in their character, become able to move forward in a positive manner. In this way, they play a purposeful role at both the individual and collective levels and become a means of constructive change in society. The challenges and difficulties of life are a part of the mental training of youth. The Qur'an instructs youth to adopt patience and steadfastness so that, despite social pressure and division, they may keep their personality balanced.

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اسْتَعِينُوا بِالصَّبْرِ وَالصَّلَاةِ إِنَّ اللَّهَ مَعَ الصَّابِرِينَ ﴿١٥٣﴾^٦

Translation: "O you who have believed, seek help through patience and prayer. Indeed, Allah is with the patient."

This verse guides youth towards mental strength and emotional balance.

Collective Consciousness and Unity

Collective consciousness is a sign of the intellectual maturity and practical cohesion of a society. When individuals rise above their personal desires and interests and give preference to collective welfare, a strong and stable social structure is formed. The Holy Qur'an has also mentioned unity and agreement as a fundamental principle and has advised to avoid discord and division. If the young generation understands collective consciousness and makes unity a part of their practical life, they can become the guarantors of positive change and progress in society. Unity not only increases mutual trust but also makes collective decisions and collective actions successful. This very unity and consciousness lead a divided society towards peace, brotherhood, and progress. For the intellectual evolution of youth in divided societies, the Qur'an declares unity and cohesion as a fundamental principle.

Moral Purification and Character Building

Purification and character building are the true foundation of human personality. When a person purifies his morals, his thoughts, actions, and behavior take a positive direction. In the Qur'an and Sunnah, it has been repeatedly emphasized that the real identity of a person is his character and morals. Good morals not only make an individual better for himself but also become a source of peace, justice, and brotherhood for the whole society. Character building is in fact the process in which youth establish their lives upon high values such as truthfulness, honesty, and sacrifice. Moral purity protects a person from negative tendencies and evils, while strong character grants him the strength to stand firm against social corruption. In this way, moral training and character building play a key role in making youth exemplary individuals and society a positive collective unity. The Holy Qur'an gives a central place to morality in the intellectual evolution of youth. To avoid lies, oppression, obscenity, and injustice, and to adopt justice, truthfulness, chastity, and righteousness is essential for mental development.

إِنَّ اللَّهَ يَأْمُرُ بِالْعَدْلِ وَالْإِحْسَانِ وَإِيتَاءِ ذِي الْقُرْبَىٰ وَيَنْهَىٰ عَنِ الْفَحْشَاءِ وَالْمُنْكَرِ وَ
الْبَغْيِ يَعِظُكُمْ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَذَكَّرُونَ ﴿٩٠﴾

Translation: "Indeed, Allah orders justice and good conduct and giving to relatives and forbids immorality and bad conduct and oppression. He admonishes you that perhaps you will be reminded."

The Holy Qur'an emphasizes faith, knowledge, patience, unity, and moral values for the intellectual development of youth. These principles not only strengthen the young generation individually but also enable them to play a balanced and constructive role at the social level. In divided societies, these teachings serve as a source of hope and guidance for the youth.

Intellectual Development of Youth in the Light of Hadith

In Islam, special importance has been given to the training and intellectual development of youth. The Holy Prophet ﷺ provided such teachings for the intellectual, moral, and

practical training of youth that not only strengthen them individually but also make them capable of playing a positive role at the social level. In divided societies, where youth face various social pressures, prejudices, and conflicts, the Hadith provides them with guidance and encouragement.

1. Worship and Intellectual Training

Divided societies have profound effects on the mental growth and intellectual development of the young generation. The differences, prejudices, and group conflicts found in such societies can incline youth toward mental distraction and intellectual division. However, the Qur'an and Hadith provide a bright source of guidance for youth that teaches them moderation, patience, justice, and unity. The Holy Qur'an encourages youth toward knowledge and wisdom, piety, and consciousness, while the sayings of the Prophet ﷺ promote tolerance, selflessness, and positive conduct in practical life. Thus, if youth establish their intellectual development on the principles of the Qur'an and Sunnah, they not only become balanced personalities individually but also prove to be guarantors of peace, unity, and social harmony in divided societies.

2. Knowledge and Intellectual Development

The most fundamental source of human intellectual development and mental maturity is knowledge. The Holy Qur'an has invited man to live life in the light of knowledge and has declared it the cause of the superiority of humanity. The Almighty has said:

"وَعَلَّمَ آدَمَ الْأَسْمَاءَ كُلَّهَا"⁸

Translation: "And He taught Adam the names - all of them."

Allah Almighty taught Adam (A.S.) the names of all things, making it clear that the true dignity of man is associated with knowledge. Through knowledge, youth not only understand their surroundings but also refine their personality and thinking. In divided societies where prejudices and differences prevail, knowledge is the power that takes youth away from negative attitudes and leads them toward positive and constructive thinking. In the Hadith of the Prophet ﷺ, knowledge is also declared as the source of guidance and intellectual development. The Messenger of Allah ﷺ said:

"طَلَبُ الْعِلْمِ فَرِيضَةٌ عَلَى كُلِّ مُسْلِمٍ"⁹

Translation: "Seeking knowledge is a duty upon every Muslim."

This teaching highlights that knowledge not only strengthens the individual intellectually but also becomes the foundation of unity and progress for the entire society. Along with knowledge, intellectual development is not possible until the youth broaden their thinking, tolerate differences of opinion, and adopt the habit of evaluating their views on the standard of the Qur'an and Sunnah. In divided societies, it is necessary for the youth not to consider knowledge merely a means of acquiring information but to regard it as a source of personality development and social reform. Thus, knowledge and intellectual development grant youth

the insight through which they can transform differences into unity and become guarantors of social stability.

3. Morality and Character Building

Morality and character building hold a fundamental place in the intellectual development of youth. In a society where division, prejudice, and mutual differences prevail, the greatest need is that youth remain firm on strong moral principles and shape their character in the light of the Qur'an and Sunnah. The Holy Qur'an has explicitly linked the success of a believer with good deeds and pure morals. Allah Almighty says:

قَدْ أَفْلَحَ الْمُؤْمِنُونَ ﴿١﴾ الَّذِينَ هُمْ فِي صَلَاتِهِمْ خِشْعُونَ ﴿٢﴾ وَالَّذِينَ هُمْ عَنْ
اللَّغْوِ مُعْرِضُونَ ﴿٣﴾ وَالَّذِينَ هُمْ لِلزَّكَاةِ فَاعِلُونَ ﴿٤﴾^١

Translation: "Certainly will the believers have succeeded, They who are during their prayer humbly submissive, And they who turn away from ill speech, And they who are observant of zakah."

That is, the success of the believers is linked with the strength of their character and the purity of their morals. If the youth shape their lives in the light of the guidance of the Qur'an and the life of the Holy Prophet ﷺ, they can remain safe from social disorder. The Messenger of Allah ﷺ said:

إِنَّ اللَّهَ بَعَثَنِي لِتَمَامِ مَكَارِمِ الْأَخْلَاقِ وَكَمَالِ مَحَاسِنِ الْأَفْعَالِ^١

Translation: "Allah the greatest sent me to perfect the morality and politeness and to take best deeds to their height."

From this saying of the Prophet ﷺ it becomes clear that the real training of the youth is possible only through morality and character building. In divided societies, moral weakness gives rise to prejudice, hatred, and enmity. On the contrary, if the youth cultivate moral qualities such as patience, tolerance, sacrifice, justice, and brotherhood within themselves, they can play an active role in ending social division. The real purpose of character building is to provide the youth with such principles that lead them not only to personal success but also to collective welfare, social unity, and peace. Morality and character building not only refine the personality of the individual but also grant the youth in divided societies the strength through which they can promote unity instead of differences, love instead of hatred, and peace instead of discord.

4. Patience, Tolerance, and Facing Hardships

In divided societies, youth face the greatest challenges that arise due to differences, prejudices, and social pressures. In such an environment, the mental development of the youth is possible only when they develop the ability of patience, tolerance, and facing hardships. In the Holy Qur'an, patience has been declared an essential part of faith. Allah Almighty says:

"وَأَصْبِرْ وَمَا صَبْرُكَ إِلَّا بِاللَّهِ وَلَا تَحْزَنْ عَلَيْهِمْ وَلَا تَكُ فِي ضَيْقٍ مِّمَّا يَمْكُرُونَ ﴿١٢٤﴾" ۱۲

Translation: "And be patient, [O Muhammad], and your patience is not but through Allah. And do not grieve over them and do not be in distress over what they conspire. "

This verse makes it clear that patience is not merely a moral quality but is the name of connecting with Allah Almighty and believing in His help. If the youth develop this belief within themselves, they can remain steadfast in any difficult situation. The Messenger of Allah ﷺ also repeatedly mentioned the virtue of patience. He ﷺ said:

"وَمَا أُعْطِيَ أَحَدٌ عَطَاءً خَيْرًا وَأَوْسَعَ مِنَ الصَّبْرِ" ۱۳

Translation: "Nobody can be given a blessing better and greater than patience."

"عَجَبًا لِأَمْرِ الْمُؤْمِنِ إِنَّ أَمْرَهُ كُلَّهُ خَيْرٌ وَلَيْسَ ذَلِكَ لِأَحَدٍ إِلَّا لِلْمُؤْمِنِ إِنْ أَصَابَتْهُ سَرَاءٌ شَكَرَ فَكَانَ خَيْرًا لَهُ وَإِنْ أَصَابَتْهُ ضَرَاءٌ صَبَرَ فَكَانَ خَيْرًا لَهُ" ۱۴

Translation: "Strange are the ways of a believer for there is good in every affair of his and this is not the case with anyone else except in the case of a believer for if he has an occasion to feel delight, he thanks (God), thus there is a good for him in it, and if he gets into trouble and shows resignation (and endures it patiently), there is a good for him in it."

This Hadith teaches the youth that mental and emotional strength is achieved through patience and tolerance. In divided societies, youth face various challenges and pressures, in such circumstances patience keeps them intellectually and practically balanced. Tolerance and facing difficulties are also necessary for the mental development of youth because in divided societies they often face issues such as injustice, deprivation, and inequality. If the youth become accustomed to enduring these conditions with patience and wisdom, they can use their energy in a positive direction and play a role in social reform. It is necessary for the youth to consider difficulties not as obstacles but as opportunities for growth and mental maturity. History bears witness that the Companions (RA) demonstrated patience and tolerance despite severe hardships and trials, as a result of which their faith and character developed extraordinary firmness. Thus, patience, tolerance, and facing difficulties enable the youth not only to strengthen their personality but also to prove themselves as leaders who lead divided societies towards peace, harmony, and development.

5. The Value of Youth and the Importance of Time

Youth is that stage of life in which a person is at the peak of energy, willpower, and mental development. This period holds fundamental significance for personality building, character formation, and determining future goals. In divided societies, the importance of youth increases even more because this generation can become the means of either social decay or reconstruction. If the youth waste their time, not only do they weaken their own personality, but the collective development of society is also affected. In the Holy Qur'an, an oath is sworn by time to make its importance clear. Allah Almighty says:

وَالْعَصْرِ ﴿١﴾ إِنَّ الْإِنْسَانَ لَفِي خُسْرٍ ﴿٢﴾ إِلَّا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا وَعَمِلُوا الصَّالِحَاتِ وَتَوَاصَوْا
بِالْحَقِّ وَتَوَاصَوْا بِالصَّبْرِ ﴿٣﴾ " ١٥

Translation: "By time, Indeed, mankind is in loss, Except for those who have believed and done righteous deeds and advised each other to truth and advised each other to patience."

This verse makes it clear that wasting time is in fact a cause of loss for a human being. If the youth spend their time in faith, good deeds, and positive activities, they can not only make their own lives successful but also contribute to the development of society. The Messenger of Allah ﷺ also emphasized the importance of youth and time.¹⁶ The Hadith clarifies the value of youth that it is the golden period of life, and wasting it in useless activities or frivolities is harmful. In divided societies, if the youth use this precious time for educational development, scholarly research, social service, and moral training, they can lead their nation from division and weakness to unity and strength. Ignoring the importance of time leads to intellectual backwardness, while proper planning and positive use of time is a guarantee of intellectual growth and mental maturity. Therefore, it is necessary for the youth to recognize their abilities, save their time from being wasted, and utilize their energy for such purposes that are beneficial for both themselves and society. The blessed Hadith provide a practical and comprehensive framework for the intellectual development of youth. Worship, knowledge, morality, patience, and valuing time make the youth strong individually, and also protect them at the social level from the effects of division and discord. The guidance of Hadith not only grants intellectual maturity to the youth but also gives them the ability to play a constructive and effective role in society.

Mental Training of Youth in the Context of Divided Societies

Divided societies, where internal conflicts, racial or religious prejudices, and social divisions are deep, affect the youth the most. In such circumstances, the mental training of youth is not only an educational and social necessity but also a religious duty. The Qur'an and Hadith provide guidance to the youth to deal with these challenges so that instead of prejudice and hatred, they may nurture their intellectual and mental development in the light of justice, patience, knowledge, and unity.

Guidance of the Qur'an

The Qur'an provides the foundation of intellectual and spiritual training for the youth. Allah Almighty says:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا قُوا أَنْفُسَكُمْ وَأَهْلِيكُمْ نَارًا وَقُودُهَا النَّاسُ وَالْحِجَارَةُ ۗ " ١٧

Translation: "O you who have believed, protect yourselves and your families from a Fire whose fuel is people and stones."

This verse highlights the responsibility of mental and moral training. Along with parents and teachers, it is also obligatory for the youth to keep their intellectual and spiritual

direction correct. Islamic teachings are especially a message for the youth of divided societies that they should avoid differences and move towards unity and mutual cooperation so that mental development may take a positive direction.

In the light of Hadith

The Messenger of Allah ﷺ drew the attention of the youth towards mental and moral training. He ﷺ said:

"خَيْرُكُمْ مَنْ تَعَلَّمَ الْقُرْآنَ وَعَلَّمَهُ" ¹⁸

Translation: "The best among you (Muslims) are those who learn the Qur'an and teach it."

The Hadith makes it clear that knowledge and the teaching of the Qur'an are the fundamental means of the intellectual maturity of the youth. Similarly, in another Hadith, he ﷺ said:

"الْمُسْلِمُ مَنْ سَلِمَ النَّاسُ مِنْ لِسَانِهِ وَيَدِهِ وَالْمُؤْمِنُ مَنْ أَمِنَهُ النَّاسُ عَلَى دِمَائِهِمْ وَأَمْوَالِهِمْ" ¹⁹

Translation: "The Muslim is the one from whose tongue and hand the people are safe, and the believer is the one from whom the people's lives and wealth are safe."

This teaching inclines the youth towards social peace, tolerance, and forbearance, which are extremely necessary in divided societies.

Practical Dimensions of Mental Training

In divided societies, the mental training of youth is possible through the following practical dimensions:

Educational training: By promoting knowledge and research, intellectual breadth and critical consciousness can be developed among the youth.

Moral training: By adopting truth, patience, and justice in the light of the Qur'an and Hadith, youth can overcome prejudices.

Spiritual training: Through worship, remembrance, and supplication, youth can increase their spiritual and mental strength.

Social awareness: It is necessary to acquaint youth with the values of social service, cooperation, and unity so that they may play a role in reducing the division of society.

Challenges Faced by Youth in Divided Societies

Youth are the guarantors of the development and stability of any society, but when society becomes a victim of division, conflicts, and mutual hatred, it is the youth who are most affected. Their mental growth and intellectual development are directly influenced by these

challenges, which create difficulties for them in determining their identity, character, and purpose of life.

1. Intellectual Confusion and Identity Crisis

In divided societies, the greatest problem faced by youth is intellectual confusion and an identity crisis. When a society is divided on political, religious, linguistic, or social grounds, the question arises in the minds of youth: What is their real identity? Are they representatives of a particular group, language, sect, or nationality, or do they possess a universal identity that connects all? Because of this confusion and contradiction, youth lose their intellectual direction, and their mental development is affected. The Holy Qur'an provides man with a balanced and clear identity. Allah Almighty said:

"هُوَ سَمَّكُمُ الْمُسْلِمِينَ مِنْ قَبْلُ وَفِي هَذَا" ٢٠

Translation: Allah named you "Muslims" before [in former scriptures].

This verse shows that the real identity of youth is Islam, not any linguistic, tribal, or regional affiliation. This universal identity of Islam saves youth from intellectual confusion and inclines them toward unity and collectiveness. The Holy Prophet ﷺ also declared faith and morality as the foundation of identity. He ﷺ said:

"مَنْ بَطَأَ بِهِ عَمَلُهُ لَمْ يُسْرِعْ بِهِ نَسَبُهُ" ٢١

Translation: "He who is slow-paced in doing good deeds, his (high) lineage does not make him go ahead."

The Hadith gives the message to youth that the real identity is through deeds and character, not through any family, linguistic, or group affiliation.

One major reason for intellectual confusion is that in divided societies, media, biased narratives, and negative propaganda incline youth toward various extremist tendencies. As a result, they set aside their real values and Islamic identity and fall into uncertainty. This condition leads them toward mental pressure, anxiety, and sometimes despair. The Holy Qur'an and Sunnah show youth the way out of this crisis. This teaching reminds youth that their real strength lies in unity and that their identity is the adherence to the Qur'an and Sunnah. In divided societies, if youth connect their identity with Islam and human service, they can not only come out of intellectual confusion but also become a source of guidance for others. Thus, they can lead their society out of division toward progress and harmony.

2. Prejudices and Sectarianism

Among the factors that most affect the intellectual development of youth in divided societies is prejudice and sectarianism. When division arises in society on linguistic, sectarian, racial, or class bases, youth fall victim to these prejudices and cannot utilize their natural abilities in a positive way. As a result, they adopt the mentality of hatred, envy, anger, and

reaction, which proves harmful not only for their personality but also for the overall progress of society. The Holy Qur'an has clearly forbidden prejudice and sectarianism:

وَلَا تَكُونُوا كَالَّذِينَ تَفَرَّقُوا وَاخْتَلَفُوا مِنْ بَعْدِ مَا جَاءَهُمُ الْبَيِّنَاتُ وَأُولَئِكَ لَهُمْ عَذَابٌ عَظِيمٌ ﴿١٠٥﴾^{٢٢}

Translation: "And do not be like the ones who became divided and differed after the clear proofs had come to them. And those will have a great punishment."

This verse highlights that prejudices and differences, even after guidance, push a person into misguidance and division. If youth adopt this guidance of the Qur'an, they can save their intellectual development from disorder. The Holy Prophet ﷺ also strictly rejected prejudices. He ﷺ said:

لَيْسَ مِنَّا مَنْ دَعَا إِلَى عَصِيَّةٍ، وَلَيْسَ مِنَّا مَنْ قَاتَلَ عَلَى عَصِيَّةٍ. وَلَيْسَ مِنَّا مَنْ مَاتَ عَلَى عَصِيَّةٍ^{٢٣}

Translation: "He who summons others to party-spirit does not belong to us; and he who dies upholding party spirit does not belong to us."

This Hadith gives a clear message to youth that a true Islamic personality rises above prejudice and division. In divided societies, when youth are raised in an environment of prejudice, intolerance, extremism, and radicalism develop in them. This causes their mental development to stagnate, and instead of positive thinking and intellectual growth, they become captive to negative attitudes. The Qur'an and Sunnah guide youth to move away from prejudices and incline toward collectiveness. The Qur'an commands:

إِنَّمَا الْمُؤْمِنُونَ إِخْوَةٌ^{٢٤}

Translation: "The believers are but brothers."

This teaching draws the attention of youth to the fact that their real affiliation is faith and brotherhood, not linguistic or group divisions. If youth cleanse their hearts and minds from prejudice in the light of the Qur'an and Hadith, they can not only guide their intellectual and mental development in a positive direction but also emerge as true personalities who establish unity, tolerance, and peace in society.

3. Negative Attitudes and Moral Decline

In divided societies, a major threat to the mental development of youth appears in the form of negative attitudes and moral decline. When society suffers from division, hatred, and intolerance, youth are most affected. In such an environment, their behavior can lean toward extremism, selfishness, envy, lying, dishonesty, and misguidance. As a result, the balance of their personality is disrupted, and they use their abilities for the decline of society rather than its betterment. The Holy Qur'an guides to avoid moral decline and adopt positive character:

"وَلَا تَقْرَبُوا الْفَوَاحِشَ مَا ظَهَرَ مِنْهَا وَمَا بَطَّنَ" ٢٥

Translation: "And do not approach immoralities - what is apparent of them and what is concealed."

This verse reminds youth that the root of moral corruption is indecency and immorality, from which staying away is essential for their mental and spiritual development. The Holy Prophet ﷺ also taught youth to avoid negative behaviors and adopt high morals. Moral training is the foundation of a true Islamic society. When youth adopt prejudice, hatred, and negative behaviors, their sense of responsibility and positive thinking disappears. In contrast, the Holy Qur'an and Hadith call them toward patience, forbearance, justice, chastity, and good character so that they can contribute to societal reform through their behavior. In divided societies, if youth firmly uphold moral values, they can not only protect their character but also safeguard their mental development from negative effects and become a beacon of guidance for society.

4. Lack of Education and Guidance

In divided societies, the greatest obstacle to the mental development of youth is the lack of education and guidance. When educational institutions lack quality, curricula fail to balance contemporary and religious requirements, and teachers limit themselves to formal education rather than character building, youth fall prey to intellectual backwardness and mental confusion. Education is not only a person's identity but also the foundation of mental development. When youth are deprived of knowledge, their decisions are based on emotions, prejudice, and uncertainty. The Prophetic Hadiths also emphasize the importance of education and guidance. The Holy Prophet ﷺ said:

"إِذَا مَاتَ الْإِنْسَانُ انْقَطَعَ عَنْهُ عَمَلُهُ إِلَّا مِنْ ثَلَاثَةٍ: إِلَّا مِنْ صَدَقَةٍ جَارِيَةٍ، أَوْ عِلْمٍ يُنْتَفَعُ بِهِ، أَوْ وَلَدٍ صَالِحٍ يَدْعُو لَهُ" ٢٦

Translation: "When a man dies, his acts come to an end, but three, recurring charity, or knowledge (by which people) benefit, or a pious son, who prays for him (for the deceased)."

This Hadith makes it clear that the true inheritance and the source of mental development is knowledge. In divided societies, when youth do not have proper guidance, they easily fall prey to others' negative thinking, false ideologies, and extremism. The lack of guidance prevents them from understanding that their real strength lies in character, education, and positive thinking. Therefore, it is necessary to make education widespread and of high quality, to make educational institutions centers of character building, and to provide youth with guidance that gives them the awareness to live a purposeful life in the light of the Qur'an and Sunnah.

5. Social and Economic Pressure

Among the factors that most affect the mental development of youth in divided societies, social and economic pressures are prominent. Social inequality, class division,

unemployment, poverty, and deprivation generate feelings of inferiority, uncertainty, and mental stress among youth. When one group controls wealth and resources while another is deprived of basic needs, the thinking of youth turns negative, creating distrust and division within them. The Holy Qur'an has declared human trials an essential part of life:

"وَلَنَبْلُوَنَّكُمْ بِشَيْءٍ مِّنَ الْخَوْفِ وَالْجُوعِ وَنَقْصٍ مِّنَ الْأَمْوَالِ وَالْأَنْفُسِ وَالثَّمَرَاتِ ۗ وَبَشِّرِ
الصَّابِرِينَ ﴿١٥٥﴾"

Translation: "And We will surely test you with something of fear and hunger and a loss of wealth and lives and fruits, but give good tidings to the patient."

This verse makes it clear that economic problems and social difficulties are part of human life, but facing them with patience and courage is a requirement of faith. The Holy Prophet ﷺ also pointed to the effects of poverty and economic hardship:

"كَادَ الْفَقْرُ أَنْ يَكُونَ كَفْرًا وَكَادَ الْحَسَدُ أَنْ يَغْلِبَ الْقَدْرَ"^{٢٨}

Translation: "It is very much likely that poverty and hunger may drive people to disbelief by objecting Allah and it is also likely that jealousy may overcome one's fate."

This Hadith shows that economic pressure can lead youth onto paths that threaten their faith and morality. In divided societies, social pressure also becomes an obstacle to the mental development of youth. Unrealistic expectations from family and society, cultural biases, and a competitive environment mentally exhaust them. In such situations, youth lose their true identity and sense of purpose, and sometimes are drawn toward negative groups or extremism. Islam emphasizes positive behavior, patience, contentment, and justice to face these pressures. The Holy Qur'an states:

"إِنَّ اللَّهَ يَأْمُرُ بِالْعَدْلِ وَالْإِحْسَانِ"^{٢٩}

Translation: "Indeed, Allah orders justice and good conduct."

It is necessary to make youth aware that they should consider their circumstances as a test from Allah, adopt patience and contentment, and use their abilities in a positive direction. At the same time, society must provide economic justice, educational opportunities, and social facilities for youth so that they can become mentally balanced and intellectually strong.

Solutions to Youth Challenges in the Light of Islamic Teachings

Islam provides comprehensive guidance to address the intellectual, social, and moral challenges faced by youth in divided societies. The Qur'an and Hadith contain teachings that not only strengthen youth individually but also lead society collectively toward unity and stability.

1. Promotion of Faith and Spiritual Attachment

The intellectual confusion, social prejudices, and economic pressures faced by youth in divided societies severely affect their mental and moral development. In such circumstances, faith and spiritual attachment become the greatest support and encouragement for youth. Faith not only keeps a person steadfast in difficulties but also grants positive thinking, purposefulness, and the true meaning of life. The Holy Qur'an describes the power of faith as a source of peace for the heart:

"أَلَا بِذِكْرِ اللَّهِ تَطْمَئِنُّ الْقُلُوبُ ﴿٢٨﴾" ٣٠

Translation: "Unquestionably, by the remembrance of Allah hearts are assured."

This verse makes youth aware that even amid worldly pressures and social discord, true peace and mental development are connected to the remembrance of Allah and faith. The Holy Prophet ﷺ emphasized the importance of spiritual attachment for youth on numerous occasions. The Hadith clarifies that a young person devoted to faith and worship not only purifies and strengthens their character but also becomes deserving of great reward in the Hereafter. In divided societies, strong faith protects youth from prejudice, negative behaviors, and moral decline. Spiritual attachment encourages them to adopt qualities such as patience, tolerance, selflessness, and forbearance, which are essential for social unity and harmony. Faith helps youth clarify their identity and understand the purpose of life. When a young person strengthens their relationship with Allah, they perceive worldly troubles as temporary and dedicate their abilities to constructive work. Islam has designated worship, remembrance of Allah, recitation of the Qur'an, and supplication as sources of mental peace and spiritual development for youth. This spiritual attachment grants youth a balanced personality that is not only personally peaceful but can also guide divided societies toward unity and stability.

2. System of Education and Training

The system of education and training serves as a fundamental pillar in the mental development and intellectual growth of youth. In divided societies, where prejudices, social inequalities, and identity crises are common, education and training are the means that provide youth with awareness, moral resilience, and intellectual maturity. Islam considers education the most important tool for shaping human personality, and its significance has been repeatedly emphasized in the Qur'an and Hadith. The importance of education is clearly highlighted in the first revelation of the Qur'an:

"اقْرَأْ بِاسْمِ رَبِّكَ الَّذِي خَلَقَ ﴿١﴾" ٣١

Translation: "Recite in the name of your Lord who created."

This verse highlights the fact that education is not only a means of worldly advancement but also a source of knowledge of the Creator and mental development. Similarly, in another place it is stated:

يَرْفَعُ اللَّهُ الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا مِنْكُمْ وَالَّذِينَ أُوتُوا الْعِلْمَ دَرَجَاتٍ" ٣٣

Translation: "Allah will raise those who have believed among you and those who were given knowledge, by degrees."

This verse presents education as a means not only for mental and spiritual development but also for societal elevation. The Holy Prophet ﷺ also emphasized the system of education and training as essential for the survival of the Ummah and the development of youth. The purpose of education is not merely to provide information but also to build character and practical training. Therefore, the Islamic system of education encourages youth to adopt values such as patience, tolerance, justice, forbearance, and unity. In divided societies, if the system of education and training remains limited to curricular knowledge and neglects practical and moral aspects, youth become prone to mental disorder and intellectual decay. In contrast, an educational system that integrates religious and worldly knowledge enables youth to think positively, strengthen their faith, cultivate high morals, and act as agents of social reform. The purpose of Islamic education and training is not only to make the individual successful but also to prepare a community that can save society from division, prejudice, and negative behaviors, guiding it towards peace, justice, and fairness.

3. Patience, Forbearance, and Self-Restraint

In divided societies, patience, forbearance, and self-restraint are fundamental qualities for the mental development of youth. These qualities not only provide inner peace to the individual but also promote social harmony and a positive mindset. In societies where prejudice, hatred, and conflicts are prevalent, if youth act with patience and self-restraint, they can protect their personality from disintegration and build a balanced and strong character. The Holy Quran repeatedly presents patience as the key to success. Allah Almighty says:

إِنَّ اللَّهَ مَعَ الصَّابِرِينَ ﴿١٥٣﴾" ٣٣

Translation: "Indeed, Allah is with the patient."

This verse reflects the reality that patience makes a person deserving of Allah's special companionship and help, which is the greatest support for the intellectual and mental development of youth. At another place, it is stated:

وَاصْبِرْ وَمَا صَبْرُكَ إِلَّا بِاللَّهِ وَلَا تَحْزَنْ عَلَيْهِمْ وَلَا تَكُ فِي ضَيْقٍ مِمَّا يَمْكُرُونَ ﴿١٢٤﴾" ٣٣

Translation: "And be patient, [O Muhammad], and your patience is not but through Allah. And do not grieve over them and do not be in distress over what they conspire."

This teaching makes youth aware that patience and self-control in the face of difficulties and a divided environment are possible not through personal strength but through trust in Allah. In the Noble Hadiths, patience and self-restraint are also counted among the

best moral qualities. Similarly, emphasizing the virtue of tolerance and controlling anger, it is stated:

لَيْسَ الشَّدِيدُ بِالصُّرَعَةِ ، إِنَّمَا الشَّدِيدُ الَّذِي يَمْلِكُ نَفْسَهُ عِنْدَ الْغَضَبِ " ٣٥

Translation: "The strong is not the one who overcomes the people by his strength, but the strong is the one who controls himself while in anger."

In divided societies, patience and self-control protect youth from emotional reactions, retaliatory behavior, and hateful thoughts. An attitude of tolerance not only grants the individual peace but also reduces social tension and promotes unity and brotherhood. From an Islamic perspective, patience and tolerance are not merely enduring difficulties but represent an active and positive approach through which youth direct their energies constructively. Through self-control, they restrain their desires and dedicate themselves to achieving higher goals.

4. Unity and Brotherhood

An important aspect of the mental development of youth in divided societies is unity and brotherhood. Social differences, prejudices, and division create confusion and conflict in the minds of youth, but Islam has established brotherhood and unity as an essential part of faith. The teachings of the Quran and Hadith convey a clear message to youth that mental and intellectual development is possible only when they set aside differences and follow the path of mutual love and cooperation. Islam teaches youth that true mental development is possible only when their relationships are based on brotherhood, selflessness, and reconciliation. This teaching makes youth aware that unity is not only a social necessity but also a religious requirement. The importance of brotherhood and unity is also emphasized in the Hadith of the Prophet ﷺ. In one Hadith, he said:

مَثَلُ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ فِي تَوَادُّهِمْ وَتَرَاحُمِهِمْ وَتَعَاطُفِهِمْ مَثَلُ الْجَسَدِ إِذَا اشْتَكَ مِنْهُ عَضْوٌ
تَدَاعَى لَهُ سَائِرُ الْجَسَدِ بِالسَّهَرِ وَالْحُمَّى " ٣٦

Translation: "The similitude of believers in regard to mutual love, affection, fellow-feeling is that of one body; when any limb of it aches, the whole body aches, because of sleeplessness and fever."

In divided societies, these teachings are highly guiding for youth, as unity and brotherhood not only protect them from prejudice and hatred but also help in forming a mentally strong, balanced, and peaceful personality. Unity attracts youth toward collective consciousness, shared goals, and positive behaviors, which are the foundational pillars for mental development.

5. Justice and Social Responsibility

For the mental development of youth in divided societies, justice and social responsibility hold fundamental importance. Where injustice, prejudice, and discrimination prevail, the mental

growth of youth is affected, giving rise to feelings of deprivation, despair, and rebellion. The teachings of the Quran and Hadith emphasize that the establishment of justice and awareness of social responsibilities are the foundation upon which a balanced and progressive society can be built. Quranic teachings instruct youth that justice is a fundamental principle in both personal and social life. In one instance, it is stated:

"وَإِذَا قُلْتُمْ فَاعْدِلُوا وَلَوْ كَانَ ذَا قُرْبَىٰ" ٣٤

Translation: "And when you testify, be just, even if [it concerns] a near relative."

This teaching highlights the importance of honesty and truthfulness in the mental development of youth. In the Prophetic traditions, special emphasis is also placed on justice and fairness. The Messenger of Allah ﷺ said:

"إِنَّ الْمُقْسِطِينَ عِنْدَ اللَّهِ عَلَىٰ مَنَابِرٍ مِنْ نُورٍ، عَنِ يَمِينِ الرَّحْمَنِ عَزَّ وَجَلَّ" ٣٨

Translation: "Behold! the Dispensers of justice will be seated on the pulpits of light beside God, on the right side of the Merciful."

Similarly, in another Hadith, it is stated:

"كُلُّكُمْ رَاعٍ وَكُلُّكُمْ مَسْئُولٌ عَنْ رَعِيَّتِهِ" ٣٩

Translation: "All of you are guardians and responsible for your wards and the things under your care."

This Hadith instills in youth the awareness that social responsibility rests upon every individual, and mental development is only possible when they act responsibly for the balance and welfare of society.

In divided societies, if youth incorporate justice and fairness into their practical lives and fulfill social responsibilities with awareness, they can not only direct their mental development positively but also guide society towards unity, peace, and progress. Islamic teachings provide youth with a complete code of life, teaching them how to address their challenges based on faith, knowledge, patience, unity, and justice. If youth adhere to these principles, they can not only overcome the challenges of divided societies but also lead society toward development, peace, and stability.

Summary

Divided societies are always prone to intellectual confusion, social discord, racial and religious prejudices, and internal conflicts. These societal divisions affect the youth the most, as youth is the most sensitive stage for mental, intellectual, and personal development. At this stage, if youth are guided positively, they play a leading role in the construction and progress of society. However, if their mental training and intellectual guidance are neglected, they fall prey to extremism, despair, and disorder. Islam provides a comprehensive guidance system for the mental development of youth through the Quran and Hadith. The Quran

teaches youth knowledge, reason, patience, unity, justice, and moderation so that they can rise above societal divisions and hatred to form a balanced personality.

Allah Almighty says:

"And hold firmly to the rope of Allah all together and do not become divided."⁴⁰

This verse highlights that unity and consensus are fundamental for avoiding societal division and directing mental development positively. Similarly, the Quran guides youth to make decisions in the light of knowledge and wisdom and to fulfill their social responsibilities properly. The Hadith of the Prophet ﷺ also emphasizes the intellectual and moral training of youth. This guidance encourages youth toward knowledge so that their mental development is based not merely on worldly desires but on Qur'anic principles. These principles motivate youth to adopt a peaceful and constructive social attitude, which is essential for divided societies. In divided societies, the mental development of youth depends on following the teachings of the Quran and Sunnah. When youth illuminate their thinking and awareness with religious principles, they develop balance, moderation, tolerance, and insight in their personality. As a result, they play an effective role in reducing social division and promoting unity and harmony. In this way, youth not only improve their own character but also guide the entire society toward progress in an environment of peace, justice, and brotherhood. Thus, it becomes clear that if the youth in divided societies are trained in the light of the Holy Quran and Hadith, they can not only foster their mental development positively but also become a guarantee of unity, peace, and progress for the entire society. In this way, a society can emerge that is based on the principles of the Quran and Sunnah, where harmony and unity prevail instead of division.

Results

This research clearly indicates that divided societies have a profound impact on the mental development of youth. The conflicts, group differences, racial and religious prejudices, and political tensions that arise in such societies fragment the personality of young individuals. However, the teachings of the Quran and Sunnah provide youth with an intellectual and practical framework through which they can not only balance their own personality but also play a key role in societal unity and stability.

1. The Quran conveys to youth the message of knowledge, awareness, unity, and justice, enabling them to rise above social differences and play a positive role.
2. The Hadith of the Prophet ﷺ emphasizes not only the intellectual training of youth but also the cultivation of tolerance, patience, altruism, and love in practical life.
3. In divided societies, youth are the group that, if properly guided, can ensure social harmony and progress.
4. According to the Quran and Hadith, the ultimate goal of mental development in youth is to make them balanced, moderate, and active individuals capable of taking a leading role in solving societal problems.

5. If youth are deprived of the teachings of the Quran and Sunnah, they fall prey to extremism, despair, and negative behaviors, which further intensifies social division.

Recommendations

1. Promotion of Quranic Teachings: Educational institutions and society should widely promote the reflective study of the Quran for youth so that they can shape their mental development in the light of divine revelation.
2. Practical Implementation of Prophetic Hadith: The training of youth should prioritize the Seerah and authentic Hadith so that they can apply these principles in practical life.
3. Curriculum Reforms: In divided societies, the curriculum should be designed to highlight the principles of unity, tolerance, and intellectual harmony.
4. Academic and Intellectual Forums: Scholarly dialogues, workshops, and seminars should be organized for youth to help them understand differences and learn to form opinions with tolerance and patience.
5. Positive Use of Social Media: In the current era, digital platforms directly influence youth; therefore, positive religious and ethical content should be promoted on these platforms.
6. Guidance and Counseling System: A structured system of guidance under the supervision of educational experts, scholars, and social leaders should be established to help youth overcome intellectual and practical dilemmas.
7. Unity-Based Policies: The state and social institutions should formulate policies that reduce social division and provide youth the opportunity to utilize their abilities in a peaceful and harmonious environment.
8. Strengthening Family Training: Parents should provide intellectual and moral education at home based on the Quran and Sunnah to ensure that the negative effects of social division do not impact the personality of youth.

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- ³⁴ **Al Quran** 16: 127.
- ³⁵ **Bukhari**, Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Ismail bin Ibrahim bin Mughira, **Sahih al-Bukhari**, V. 7, Kitab: The Book of Al- Adab (Good Manners), Chapter: To be cautious from being angry, Hadith 6114.
- ³⁶ **Muslim**, Muslim ibn Hajaj al Qushairi, Imam, Neeshapuri, **Sahih Muslim**, V. 6, Kitab: The Book of Virtue, Enjoining Good Manners, and Joining of the Ties of Kinshio, Chapter: The Mutual Mercy, Compassion And Support Of The Believers, Hadith No. 6586/ 2586.
- ³⁷ **Al Quran** 6: 152.
- ³⁸ **Muslim**, Muslim ibn Hajaj al Qushairi, Imam, Neeshapuri, **Sahih Muslim**, V. 5, Kitab: The Book of Government, Chapter: The virtue of a just ruler and the punishment of a tyrant; Encouragement to treat those under one's authority with kindness and the prohibition against causing them hardship, Hadith No. 4721/ 1827.
- ³⁹ I. **Bukhari**, Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Ismail bin Ibrahim bin Mughira, **Sahih al-Bukhari**, V. 2, Kitab: The Book of Al- Jumuah (Friday), Chapter: To offer the Salat-ul-Jumuah [prayer and Khutba (religious talk)] in villages and towns, Hadith No. 893.

II. **Muslim**, Muslim ibn Hajaj al Qushairi, Imam, Neeshapuri, **Sahih Muslim**, V. 5, Kitab: The Book of Government, Chapter: The virtue of a just ruler and the punishment of a tyrant; Encouragement to treat those under one's authority with kindness and the prohibition against causing them hardship, Hadith No. 4724/ 1829.

⁴⁰ **Al Quran** 3:103.